

A Comparison of Urinary Iodine Concentration Between Individuals Without and With Hashimoto's Thyroiditis

A. Oblak¹, S. Gaberšček^{1,2}, M. Hribar³, M. Gregorič⁴, U. Blaznik⁴, A. Kušar³, K. Žmitek³, I. Pravst³, K. Zaletel^{1,2}

¹Department of Nuclear Medicine, University Medical Centre Ljubljana, SI-1000 Ljubljana, SLOVENIA,

²Faculty of Medicine, University of Ljubljana, SI-1000 Ljubljana, SLOVENIA,

³Nutrition Institute, SI-1000 Ljubljana, SLOVENIA,

⁴National Institute of Public Health, SI-1000 Ljubljana, SLOVENIA.

Abstract:

Aim/Introduction: Dietary iodine intake has an important influence on the occurrence of thyroid disorders. Excessive iodine intake is associated with a higher prevalence of autoimmune thyroid disease Hashimoto's thyroiditis (HT). By contrast, HT with elevated thyroglobulin antibodies (anti-Tg) and/or thyroid peroxidase antibodies (anti-TPO) is less common in regions with iodine deficiency. In the year 2009, the incidence of HT in Slovenia was significantly higher than in the year 1999, when an increase in the kitchen salt iodination from 10 to 25 mg of potassium iodide per kilogram of salt was adopted. This increase in salt iodination resulted in adequate iodine intake in Slovenia. World health organization (WHO) proposes periodical measurements of urinary iodine concentration (UIC) in single spot urine for the assessment of iodine supply in a population. Our aim was to re-evaluate the UIC in Slovenian population and to compare UIC values between individuals without and with HT.

Materials and Methods: In the Nutrihealth study 620 participants representing a nationally representative sample of adults were invited to participate, after participating in national dietary survey Si.Menu. Two hundred and eighty participants provided biological samples, urine and serum. Collection of biological samples was carried out from June 2017 to September 2018. Serum anti-TPO and anti-Tg were analysed using immunochemiluminiscent detection on Advia Centaur XP. Cut-off for positive anti-Tg and anti-TPO was set to 60 kU/L. UIC was determined spectrophotometrically with absorbance at 405 nm by Sandell-Kolthoff method with ammonium pretreatment digestion. Statistical software MedCalc was used for evaluation of the results.

Results: Out of 280 participants, data from 7 participants were not included into analysis of results because UIC determination was above or below measurement range (< 5 µg/L or > 400 µg/L, respectively). Forty-eight participants (17.6%) had increased level of anti-TPO and/or anti-Tg and thus represented a group with HT. Two hundred and twenty five participants (82.4%) represented a group without HT. Median age of participants was 67 years (19-76). Mean values of UIC between the group without HT and the group with HT were not statistically different (103.4 µg/L and 98.8 µg/L, respectively, p=0.647).

Conclusion: Our results revealed that UIC measurements are around 100 µg/L which places Slovenia into iodine sufficient regions according to WHO criteria. We did not observe any significant changes in UIC values between individuals without and with HT.